

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS. PART I. CHROMIUM BIGUANIDINES.

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Complex compounds of bivalent metals like Cu, Co and Ni with biguanides, both as free metallic bases and their salts, have long been described (Rathke, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 779; Emich, *Monatsh.*, 1883, 4, 408; Smolka and Friedrich, *ibid.*, 1888, 9, 227). Besides the simple biguanide, various substituted products of the same, such as the methyl, ethyl and phenyl derivatives, were employed. With each atom of the bivalent metals two molecules of the biguanide base or its salts were found to be associated in the complex formed. The constitution of these interesting complex compounds of strong characteristic colour has not yet been satisfactorily cleared up in spite of repeated investigations on the subject.

The constitution of the biguanide is represented by the formula (I), which is related to those of biuret and guanyl urea. The various constitutions of metallic biguanide complexes, as suggested by different workers (Tschugaef, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 1973, formula II; Ley and Müller, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2950, formula III and IV; Slotta and Tschesche, *Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1390, formula IV; Traube, *Ber.*, 1930, 63, 2094, formula V), are given below.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V).

(VI)

[where $\text{X} = \text{OH}^-$ or any other equivalent anion, and $\text{Me} = \text{Cu}^{++}, \text{Co}^{++}, \text{Ni}^{++}$].

In order to obtain more definite information on the point we have started a systematic investigation on the preparation and properties of a series of biguanide complexes of trivalent metals such as chromium, cobalt, iridium, etc. In the present paper we shall confine ourselves only to the chromium complexes of the simple unsubstituted biguanide.

In these chromium complexes each chromium atom is associated with three biguanide molecules and, as the trivalent chromium can exhibit a maximum co-ordination number of six only, each biguanide molecule behaves as a bidentate group occupying two co-ordination positions in the complex. Further, the free chromium biguanide has been obtained in the anhydrous condition having the composition $\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_6)_3$, as well as the monohydrate $\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_6)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. This hydrate forms beautiful, brilliant red crystals, whereas the colour of the anhydrous base, which behaves like ammonia or amines, is somewhat lighter. In solution, however, the complex behaves as a triacidic base. It gives characteristically coloured solid salts of the type $\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_6)_3 \cdot 3\text{HX}$, where X denotes any monovalent anion or its equivalent. The fact that each biguanide molecule occupies two co-ordination positions, disposes of the constitutions (III) and (IV) suggested by Ley and Müller (*loc. cit.*), as well as by Slotta and Tschesche (*loc. cit.*), for the bivalent copper, cobalt and nickel biguanide complexes, in which each biguanide molecule is made to occupy three co-ordination positions, making a biva-

lent metal atom exhibit a maximum co-ordination number of six. Ley and Müller, as well as Slotta and Tschesche, assume that it is the hydrogen atom of the central imino-group which is displaced by the metal atom, and the latter unites with the nitrogen of the imino-group on both sides forming inner metallic complexes. On the other hand, Ley and Werner (*Ber.*, 1913, 46, 4040) assign a quite different constitution to the copper biuret complex (VII), though the constitutions of biuret and biguanide are closely analogous.

(VII)

In addition, the metal atom in these complexes (III and IV) forms a member of fused four-membered rings, which, as has been established by Werner and Pfeiffer, can seldom be stable, whereas the stability of biguanide metal complexes exceeds that of most of the well-known inner-metallic salts. Furthermore, formula (IV) leaves four NH_2 -groups in the molecule in a free state. Hence the biguanide complexes of the three bivalent metals should behave as tetra-acidic bases, whereas they are actually diacidic. According to formula (III), on the other hand, the complex should behave as a neutral body, unless we assume that the imino-groups exert some basic character.

From a study of the increase of acidity by the introduction of metallic atoms into molecules of organic bases or hydroxy compounds, Traube (*loc. cit.*) suggested the constitution (V) for these biguanide metal complexes. The formula does not take note of the co-ordination valencies of copper and hence does not represent the compound as an inner-metallic complex salt which alone can account for its intense colour. Further, the copper atom is shown to replace the hydrogen atoms of one of the end-amino groups of the biguanide base, which is rather unusual and cannot be justified.

Finally, Tschugaeff's formula (II) is also rendered untenable by the fact that it does not represent the complex as an inner-metallic salt, since the central metal atom is linked with the N-atoms of the four amino-groups by co-ordination valencies as in copper tetrammine compounds. The preparation of the anhydrous $\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_6)_3$ by us definitely proves that the primary valencies of the metal atom are satisfied by the removal of one

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hydrogen atom from each biguanide molecule, and that the basic character of these compounds is due to free amino-groups, and not to the metal atom whose valencies, both normal and co-ordinative, are fully saturated.

From the considerations set forth above it becomes quite clear that the biguanide metal complexes are of the inner-metallic complex salt type; but at the same time they can behave as basic compounds and form salts with acids due to the free amino-groups co-ordinating with H-ions. Each biguanide molecule behaves as a bidentate or chelate group and is linked to the central metal atom both by a primary as well as a secondary valency, like glycine or other amino-acids. Slotta and Tschesche (*loc. cit.*), from the fact that 1:2:3-triphenylbiguanide gives no complex metallic compound, whereas 1:2-diphenylbiguanide and phenylbiguanide give respectively soluble and insoluble metallic complexes, concluded that the hydrogen of the central imino-group is essential for complex formation and is replaced by the metal atom. The argument is not very convincing. Because, the inactivity of the above-mentioned tri-substituted biguanide may be due either to its insolubility in water, or to its enhanced inertness as the result of multiple substitution by phenyl groups. For, we have found that metallic complexes with phenyl (mono) biguanide are less easily formed and are less stable than those with unsubstituted biguanide.

That a hydrogen atom of the imino-group linked to a carbon atom by a double bond can be replaced by a heavy metal atom to give rise to co-ordination compounds of the type discussed here, is best illustrated by the existence of certain complex copper compounds of aminoguanidine of the following composition described by Thiele (*Annalen*, 1892, 270, 1).

In these compounds none of the hydrogen atoms of the amino- or the hydrazino-group of the aminoguanidine is likely to be replaced by the metal atom. It is the hydrogen atom of the imino-group that is replaced by the copper atom co-ordinating simultaneously with the end nitrogen of the hydrazino-group to form a five-membered ring.

We, therefore, suggest the formula (VI) for the biguanide complexes of bivalent metals and the formula (VIII) for those with a trivalent metal like chromium. In these, the metal atoms enter into six-membered rings contributing to the stability of the complex, and the number of free amino-groups corresponds to the acidity of the complex base formed. A similar suggestion for the constitution of the biguanide complexes of the bivalent metals has also been offered by Stumpf (Dissertation, Berlin, 1933, p. 24).

(VIII)

These chromium *trisbiguanide* salts undergo slow but gradual hydrolysis on warming in dilute solutions, or on keeping, giving rise to a series of hydrolysed products. This is more evident with a solution of the complex hydrate. The mode of hydrolysis may be represented as follows:—

[BigH = One molecule
of biguanide].

The description of the preparation and properties of these hydrolysed products will form the subject matter of subsequent communications; those of the chromium *trisbiguanide* hydroxide and its salts, and a discussion of their constitution have been dealt with in the present paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Chromium Trisbiguanide Monohydrate.—A saturated solution of chrome alum was added, drop by drop, with stirring to a cold solution of biguanide sulphate in an excess of strong caustic liquor (30% NaOH). A dark red solution was obtained without any noticeable separation of chromium hydroxide, and bright red prismatic crystals separated readily from the solution in quantities. The solution with the crystals was cooled in ice until no more solid separated and was then filtered on the pump. The crystals were washed with cold water, purified by recrystallisation from hot water in presence of a little caustic soda and dried in air, free from carbon dioxide. {Found: N, 57·16, 57·03; Cr, 13·96, 13·93, 14·06. $[(\text{Big})_3 \text{Cr} (\text{BigH})^+] \text{OH}$ requires N, 56·76; Cr, 14·05 per cent}.

The substance is of beautiful crimson-red colour, which appears ruby-red in large crystals. The crystals are moderately soluble in water, and the solution is strongly alkaline. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salts, precipitates hydroxides of heavy metals from solutions of their salts and behaves as a tri-acidic base in aqueous solution.

0·3966 G. of the substance required 3·32 c.c. *N*-HCl for neutralization. $[\text{Cr} (\text{BigH})_3^+] (\text{OH})_3$ requires 3·21 c.c. *N*-HCl.

As the solution was strongly coloured and the titration was not carried out potentiometrically but with outside litmus paper indicator, this discrepancy was not unexpected. Measurement of the molecular conductivity and the freezing point of the solution of the base also leads to the same conclusion.

Molecular conductivity at 29°.

ν (dilution) ...	32	64	128	256	512	1024
$\mu\nu$...	132·9	187·2	235·7	292·2	346·2	404·1

The values at higher dilutions are likely to be somewhat vitiated by hydrolysis.

The equivalent conductivity of the base deduced from the above values may be compared with those for ammonia, amines, biguanide and copper biguanide.

Equivalent conductivity for the bases.

ν (dilation)	10.7	21.4	42.8	85.6	171.2	} Temp. = 29°.	
λ_{ν}	44.3	62.4	78.6	97.4	115.4		
ν	8	16	32	64	128		256
$\lambda_{\nu} \text{NH}_3$	3.21	4.35	6.52	9.29	13.4	19.0	} Temp. = 25°.*
$\lambda_{\nu} \text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$	15.1	21.0	28.9	39.3	53.9	70.0	
$\lambda_{\nu} (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NH}$	17.2	24.0	33.2	45.3	61.2	80.7	

* Walden, das Leitvermögen der Lösungen—II Teile. pp. 82-83, 1924.

ν	300	450	900	} Temp. = 37°-†
λ_{ν} Biguanide	153.0	153.0	157.5	
λ_{ν} Cu-bisbiguanide	74.0	76.5	91.5	

† Deduced from Stumpf's data (*loc. cit.* p. 41)

A comparison of the above values indicates that the chromium *tris*-biguanide hydroxide is a considerably stronger base than ammonia, methylamine, dimethylamine and copper-*bis*biguanide hydroxide, but appears to be somewhat weaker than the free biguanide hydroxide. This comparison is evidently a very rough one due to the differences in temperature of measurements, for which proper allowances should be made.

Definite evidences regarding the tri-acidic nature of the base, are, however, furnished by the preparation of a series of crystalline salts of the base as described hereafter, in which a molecule of the base is found to combine with three equivalents of the acid, as well as by determination of the valency of the complex ion with the help of Ostwald-Walden's rule from the measurement of equivalent conductivity of its hydrochloride.

A determination of the freezing point of an aqueous solution of the base also supports the above conclusions.

Molecular weight from the freezing-point.

Substance (g/100 c.c.)	Depression, Δ	Mol. wt. m	Vant Hoff's factor $i = M/m$	Degree of dissociation. $\alpha = i - 1/n - 1.$
0.2496	0.04°	115	370/115 = 3.217	0.75

[where M = mol. wt. calculated; n = number of ions into which the base is dissociated = 4].

The magnetic susceptibility of the substance measured in a Curies balance at 31° gave a value of $\chi_m = 16.47 \times 10^{-6}$, whence $P_{\text{Weiss}} = 19.15$, which is almost identical with those for all complex chromium amines and salts, as well as for the simple chromium ion— Cr^{+++} .

The substance decomposes on prolonged boiling with mineral acids giving rise to chromic salts. Strong boiling alkali precipitates chromium hydroxide from a solution of the substance with evolution of ammonia.

On keeping a cold alkaline solution of the chromium *trisbiguanide* hydroxide for some time, the red colour of the solution gradually turns reddish violet and rose-red silky crystals of a hydrolysed product are occasionally deposited from the solution. A similar change occurs with the dilute aqueous solution of the base itself.

Chromium Trisbiguanidine.—The monohydrate $[\text{Cr}(\text{Big})_3]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ did not lose any weight on being kept over concentrated H_2SO_4 in vacuum. When heated, however, to $150\text{--}160^\circ$ for about 40 hours it lost 4.84% of its weight.

Percentage of water in the monohydrate = 4.87. When heated to 200° , the substance commences to decompose. [Found : N, 59.41. $\text{Cr}(\text{Big})_3$ requires N, 59.67 per cent].

This anhydro-base is insoluble in all organic solvents. It readily absorbs water to regenerate the monohydrate. The anhydro-base is brick-red in colour.

Chromium Trisbiguanide Hydrochloride.—This was prepared by treating the solid base in a mortar with cold (ice cooling) dilute hydrochloric acid till the mixture became slightly acid. The yellow crystals of the hydrochloride formed were filtered and washed with a little ice-cold water. The crude crystals were then dissolved in the least quantity of hot water, the solution was filtered and cooled in ice. Pure crystals of the hydrochloride separated from the filtrate. The yield of the product could be increased by adding a saturated solution of ammonium chloride to the filtrate. The crystals were filtered, washed at first with ice-cold water and then with absolute alcohol. These were dried in air.

The hydrochloride was also prepared by the action of ammonium chloride upon the base. When the solid base was rubbed in a mortar with a concentrated solution of ammonium chloride, the hydrochloride of the base was formed with evolution of ammonia. {Found : N, 45.2, 45.4; Cl, 23.14, 23.11; Cr, 11.32, 11.35. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]\text{Cl}_3$ requires N, 45.50; Cl, 23.08; Cr, 11.27 per cent}. The substance forms yellow octahedral crystals, soluble in water.

Equivalent conductivity at 30°.

v (dilution)	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_v	97.05	106.0	115.7	122.6	128.8	134.8	139.3
λ_{∞}	147.4	145.0	145.6	145.0	145.5	147.2	148.0
Mean λ_{∞}	146.0						

λ_{32} (after 5 days) = 97.16.

The λ_{∞} value is calculated from Walden's formula :—

$\lambda_{\infty} = \lambda_v (1 + n_1 \cdot n_2 \times 0.692 \times v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$, where v = dilution, n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.

The valency of the complex ion, according to Ostwald-Walden's rule, is given by $\lambda_{1024} - \lambda_{32} = 139.3 - 106.0 = 33.3 = 3.33 \times 10$. The valency is, therefore, three.

The equivalent conductivity of the salt can also be compared with those of complex chromium ammine salts having the same valency for the cation, as well as with those of LaCl_3 .

Temperature = 25°.

v (dilution)	125	250	500	1000
μ_v for $[\text{Cr}(\text{CO}(\text{NH}_2)_2)_3]\text{Cl}_3$	296.5	315.4	326.0	340.5

(Werner and Kalkmann, *Annalen*, 1902, 322, 313).

v	32	64	128	256	512	1024	∞
λ_v for LaCl_3	113.1	119.8	126.1	131.9	136.1	140.6	150

(Ley, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 30, 236).

Making allowances for temperature differences, the results are found to compare quite favourably. The values of μ_v for chromium hexaurea chloride can be reduced to those for the corresponding equivalent dilutions. The results further indicate that the mobility of the complex chromium trisbiguanide ion is nearly of the same order as that of the complex chromium hexaurea cation and considerably lower than that of La^{+++} -ion.

It was found that the equivalent conductivity of the chromium trisbiguanide hydrochloride decreased on keeping its solution, as the result for

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λ_{39} after 5 days' keeping indicates. This is, however, difficult to account for. On the other hand, from the fact that a dilute solution of the salt on keeping undergoes slow hydrolysis, exactly the contrary result might have been expected. This anomaly is possibly connected with a strange property of the solution of the hydrochloride and hydrobromide. From a freshly prepared solution of the hydrochloride all the chlorine is precipitated as AgCl by silver nitrate solution at the room temperature, though the precipitation does not appear to be complete instantaneously and requires shaking for a few moments. But after keeping this solution for 24 hours, addition of silver nitrate produces only a strong turbidity, the addition of a neutral salt like ammonium nitrate, however, immediately precipitates the whole of the chloride as AgCl. This proves that no constitutional change occurs in the aged solution, but the latter develops a power similar to that of protective colloids in preventing the growth of silver chloride particles. This behaviour has been found to be more pronounced in the case of the hydrochloride of the hydrolysed base which will be described in a future communication.

Determination of the molecular weight by freezing-point method supported the conclusion from conductivity measurements.

Subs. (g./100 c.c.)	Depression. Δ	Mol. wt. m	Vant Hoff's factor $i = M/m$	Degree of dissociation $\alpha = i - 1/n - 1$
0.7198	0.11°	117.8	3.92	0.97

[where M and n have the usual significance].

The result shows that even at 0°, the substance dissociates almost completely into four ions and the whole of the chlorine is in the ionic state.

The yellow solution of the hydrochloride, on keeping for a long time slowly turns violet and deposits rose-red crystals of a hydrolysed product. A similar change of colour at first occurs on boiling the solution, but finally decomposition sets in with separation of chromium hydroxide.

Chromium trisbiguanide hydrobromide was obtained as orange-yellow crystals, moderately soluble in water, by adding a concentrated solution of potassium bromide to a strong solution of the complex hydrochloride. The crystals were filtered, washed and dried over H_2SO_4 . {Found : Br, 40.10 ; Cr, 8.83. $[Cr(BigH_2^+)_3] Br_3$ requires Br, 40.30; Cr, 8.74 per cent}.

Chromium trisbiguanide hydriodide was prepared like the previous compound from the complex hydrochloride and potassium iodide. The subs-

tance forms orange-yellow crystals which are much less soluble in water than those of the hydrochloride. The crystals were washed and dried as before. {Found : N, 28'30 ; I, 51'24 ; Cr, 7'12. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_3]_3 \text{I}_3$ requires N, 28'53 ; I, 51'76 ; Cr, 7'06 per cent}.

Chromium trisbiguanide sulphate was obtained in the form of sparingly soluble, orange-yellow, needle-shaped crystals when a solution of ammonium sulphate was added to that of the complex hydrochloride. The crystals were washed with cold water and dried in air. {Found : N, 40'53 ; Cr, 10'02 ; SO_4 , 27'70. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_3]_3 (\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 40'62 ; Cr, 10'06 ; SO_4 , 27'85 per cent}. A tetrahydrate is sometimes formed as long (1 cm.) needle-shaped prismatic crystals with orange-red colour.

Chromium trisbiguanide nitrate was prepared by adding a concentrated solution of potassium nitrate to a cold concentrated solution of the complex hydrochloride. The mixture was cooled in ice. The crystals separated were filtered, washed at first with ice-cold water and finally with alcohol. They were afterwards dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The substance forms orange-yellow crystals, readily soluble in water. {Found : N, 46'50 ; Cr, 9'62. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] (\text{NO}_3)_3$ requires N, 46'60 ; Cr, 9'64 per cent}.

Chromium trisbiguanide nitrite was prepared like the previous compound from the complex hydrochloride and potassium nitrite. It resembles the nitrate in colour and other properties. {Found : N, 50'80 ; Cr, 10'64. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] (\text{NO}_2)_3$ requires N, 51'10 ; Cr, 10'53 per cent}.

Chromium Trisbiguanide Chlorocarbonate.—When a strong solution of sodium carbonate was added to a cold concentrated solution of the complex hydrochloride, the orange-yellow crystals of the chlorocarbonate separated from the solution. The mixture was cooled in ice. The crystals that separated were then filtered, washed and dried as in the case of the chromium *trisbiguanide nitrate*. The substance readily dissolves in water giving a solution, strongly alkaline to litmus. {Found : C, 17'24 ; Cl, 15'60 ; Cr, 11'48, 11'44. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 \text{CO}_2\text{Cl}_4$ requires C, 17'10 ; Cl, 15'57 ; Cr, 11'40 per cent}.

Chromium trisbiguanide carbonate was prepared by adding three molecular proportions of sodium bicarbonate to a cold concentrated solution of chromium *trisbiguanide hydroxide*. The mixture was cooled in ice and the normal carbonate was salted out by the addition of a saturated solution of sodium carbonate. The crystals were washed and dried as in the previous case. {Found : C, 19'50 ; Cr, 11'20. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 (\text{CO}_3)_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 19'40 ; Cr, 11'23 per cent}.

The substance forms orange-yellow crystals, readily soluble in water.

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The solution is strongly alkaline to litmus and liberates ammonia from ammonium salts on warming.

Chromium Trisbiguanide Hydrosulphide.—A solution of the chromium trisbiguanide base was treated with a few drops of ammonia and then saturated in the cold with H_2S . The crystalline precipitate formed was filtered, washed first with ice-water and afterwards with absolute alcohol. The crystals were dried by pressing between filter-papers and keeping overnight in closed air.

The substance forms brownish orange crystals, sparingly soluble in water, and gives out smell of hydrogen sulphide. It reacts alkaline to litmus. {Found : S, 19'90, 20'0; Cr, 11'90, 11'20. $[Cr(Big\overset{+}{H})_3] (HS)$, requires S, 21'10; Cr, 11'45 per cent}.

Comparatively low result for sulphur and high values for chromium indicate slight loss of H_2S .

Chromium trisbiguanide chlorosulphite was obtained as a golden yellow crystalline precipitate by adding a freshly prepared concentrated solution of sodium sulphite to the cold concentrated solution of the complex hydrochloride. The mixture was then cooled in ice and the crystals were washed first with ice-cold water and then with absolute alcohol. They were then dried, by pressing between filter-papers and keeping overnight in closed air. The salt is moderately soluble in water. {Found : Cl, 7'10; S, 6'55; Cr, 10'6. $[Cr(Big\overset{+}{H})_3] ClSO_3, H_2O$ requires Cl, 7'27; S, 6'55; Cr, 10'64 per cent}.

Chromium Trisbiguanide Hydroxosulphite.—When a freshly prepared solution of bisulphite was added, drop by drop, to an ice-cold concentrated solution of the chromium trisbiguanide hydroxide until the base was partially neutralised, orange-yellow crystals of the hydroxosulphite separated from the solution. These were washed and dried as in the previous case. The crystals are moderately soluble in water and their solution is alkaline to litmus.

{Found : S, 6'23; Cr, 10'70. $[Cr(Big\overset{+}{H})_3] \begin{matrix} SO_3 \\ OH \end{matrix}, 2\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires S, 6'44; Cr, 10'46 per cent}.

Chromium trisbiguanide chlorothiosulphate was precipitated in the form of orange coloured silky crystals by adding a solution of sodium thio-sulphate to that of the complex hydrochloride. The crystals were washed at first with cold water and then with alcohol. These were afterwards dried in air. The substance is sparingly soluble in water. {Found : Cl, 7'10;

S, 12.50; Cr, 16.40. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_3] \text{Cl} \cdot \text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ requires Cl, 7.06; S, 12.70; Cr, 10.35 per cent}

Chromium Trisbiguanide Thiosulphate—When a solution of the chromium trisbiguanide hydroxide was mixed with a solution of sodium thiosulphate in the cold and to the mixture a solution of ammonium acetate was added, silky, light orange crystals of the normal thiosulphate were precipitated. These were washed and dried as in the previous case. This normal thiosulphate is very sparingly soluble

in water. {Found: S, 18.20; Cr, 10.02. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_3]_2 (\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3$ requires S, 18.46; Cr, 10.0 per cent}.

Chromium trisbiguanide chlorochromate was obtained as a dark yellow crystalline precipitate when a solution of potassium chromate was added to that of the complex hydrochloride. The crystals were washed with ice-cold water and dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The substance is sparingly soluble in water. {Found: N, 39.50; Cl, 6.80, 6.98; Cr (total),

20.0, 19.90; Cr (as CrO''_4), 9.90. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_3] \text{Cl} \cdot \text{CrO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 40.07; Cl, 6.80; Cr (total), 19.80; Cr (as CrO''_4), 9.90 per cent}.

Chromium Trisbiguanide Chromate.—When a solution of potassium dichromate (1.2 g.) was added to a solution of the complex base (1 g.) in the cold, sparingly soluble yellowish brown crystals of the normal chromate separated out. These were washed and dried as in the case of the previous compound. {Found: Cr (total), 22.75, 22.50; Cr (as CrO''_4),

13.36, 13.10. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_3]_2 (\text{CrO}_4) \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, requires Cr (total), 22.64; Cr (as CrO''_4), 13.58 per cent}.

Chromium Trisbiguanide Perchromate.—When 30 % hydrogen peroxide (perhydrol) was added, drop by drop, to an ice-cold solution of the chromium trisbiguanide hydroxide, dark yellowish brown crystals of the perchromate separated out from the solution. A part of the complex cation was oxidised to perchromate which combined with the rest of the cation to form the very sparingly soluble perchromate of the complex cation. The crystals were washed with ice-cold water and dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The perchromate decomposes, when acidified, to a blue solution; the blue colour, however, disappears rapidly with the formation of green chromic salt. The substance gave on analysis:—

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Cr (total), 16'94, 17'20; N, 35'10; O (total), 11'50 (gasometrically), 12'0, on correcting for the chromate left in the solution after the evolution of oxygen. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^{\dagger})_3] \text{CrO}_3, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cr (total), 17'10; N, 34'60; O (total), 13'10 per cent.

Low result for oxygen is evidently due to slight decomposition of the perchromate.

Chromium trisbiguanide chlorophosphate was obtained as a sparingly soluble, flesh-coloured crystalline precipitate by adding a solution of disodium hydrogen phosphate to a solution of the complex chloride. The crystals were washed first with cold water and then with alcohol. These were afterwards dried in air. {Found: Cl, 7'20; P, 6'36; Cr, 10'54. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^{\dagger})_3] \text{HPO}_4^{\text{Cl}}$ requires Cl, 7'30; P, 6'38; Cr, 10'70 per cent.}.

Chromium trisbiguanide camphorsulphonate was obtained as a salmon-coloured crystalline precipitate by neutralising a cold concentrated solution of the complex base with a cold strong solution of camphorsulphonic acid. The crystals were first washed with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. They were afterwards dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . The salt is moderately soluble in water. {Found: S, 9'30; Cr, 5'13. $[\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^{\dagger})_3] (\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{OSO}_3)_3$ requires S, 9'16; Cr, 5'0 per cent.}.

From the filtrate of this normal sulphonate a red-violet hydrolysed product was obtained, which will be described in a separate paper.

S U M M A R Y .

1. Chromium trisbiguanide hydrate, $[(\text{Big})_2\text{Cr}(\text{BigH}^{\dagger})]\text{OH}$, which behaves as a fairly strong triacidic base in solution, has been prepared in the form of brilliant crimson-red crystals.

2. It has been shown that the complex cation is of the inner-metallic salt type with chromium as the central atom, whose normal valencies are completely saturated by the replacement of one of the hydrogen atoms in each biguanide molecule. The valency of the cation is, therefore, entirely

due to the free amino-groups of the biguanide molecules. This has been definitely proved by the preparation of the anhydrous base, $[\text{Cr}(\text{Big})_3]$, chromium trisbiguanidine. Each biguanide molecule is thus found to behave as a bidentate or chelate group occupying two co-ordination positions in the molecule.

3. A series of salts of the base have been prepared and their properties studied, *viz.*, hydrochloride, hydrobromide, sulphate, nitrate, nitrite, carbonate, chlorocarbonate, hydrosulphide, chlorosulphite, hydroxo-sulphite, thiosulphate, chlorothiosulphate, chlorophosphate, chlorochromate, chromate, perchromate and camphorsulphonate.

4. Indications have been obtained that both the base and the salts undergo slow hydrolysis in dilute aqueous solution giving rise to a series of hydrolysed products.

5. Constitution of the biguanide complexes of bi- and tervalent metals has been fully discussed.

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